

Acceleration with and without g of a Smartphone Pendulum

Michael Ziese

Leipzig University, Faculty of Physics and Earth System Sciences
D-04103 Leipzig, Germany
ziese@physik.uni-leipzig.de

December 19, 2024

Abstract

Acceleration with and without g as well as angular velocity of a smartphone pendulum were measured. Acceleration measurements in an accelerated frame of reference are discussed, the measured acceleration is modelled using the measured angular velocity and the difference between the two types of acceleration measurements is clarified.

1 Introduction

The smartphone gyroscope and acceleration sensors might be efficiently used to study pendulum motion in a classroom, physics laboratory or a home experiment [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. To this end the smartphone is used as a pendulum bob to measure angular velocity and acceleration and the data can be either recorded on the smartphone or accessed remotely from a computer. Whereas in the inertial laboratory frame of reference the acceleration of gravity is often the only acceleration acting on the smartphone, the acceleration is measured in the accelerated frame of reference of the smartphone. This leads to the appearance of additional “virtual” acceleration contributions such as the centrifugal and Coriolis acceleration which are known from the study of motion in a rotating frame of reference. These virtual acceleration terms often lead to surprising results. The acceleration sensor yields two acceleration vectors, namely the acceleration and the “acceleration without g ”, in which the contribution of the acceleration of gravity was subtracted. The aim of this work is to analyze and interpret acceleration data recorded by an oscillating smartphone to clarify the meaning of the various acceleration contributions. Further, results obtained with an iPad Air and a Huawei Mate 9 are compared.

2 Experimental Details

A sketch of the pendulum is shown in Fig. 1(a), the experimental realization using an iPad Air 3 in a 3D printed frame in Fig. 1(c). The acceleration sensor is usually not positioned at the center of the smartphone. This is schematically indicated in Fig. 1(b) with a sensor location shifted by the vector (x_S, y_S) with respect to the center of the smartphone. With respect to the suspension point P the acceleration sensor is located at $\vec{r}_S = (x_S, y_S, -l)$, where l denotes the distance between P and the center of mass. The axes directions of the iPad coordinate system are indicated. The iPad oscillates around the y -axis. The data collection was facilitated with the app “phyphox” [10], measuring angular velocity $\vec{\omega}$, acceleration \vec{a} and “acceleration without g ”, here denoted by \vec{b} , simultaneously. Further experiments were performed with a Huawei Mate 9 smartphone in the same pendulum configuration, albeit without printed frame. Data collection was made with maximum rate. In case of the iPad the reading rate was 99.6 Hz for all three sensors, in case of the

Figure 1: (a) Sketch of the pendulum. CM indicates the center of mass, φ_y the angular deflection, xyz the frame of reference attached to the device. (b) Schematic front view of the smartphone with axis conventions and the acceleration sensor position (x_S, y_S) indicated. (c) iPad Air as pendulum with axis conventions.

Mate 9 reading rates were different with 200 Hz for the gyroscope, 250 Hz for the accelerometer and 100 Hz for the “acceleration without g ”. Tests with fixed reading rate settings of 100 Hz and 10 Hz yielded actual reading rates of 82.2 Hz, 83.3 Hz, 64.5 Hz and 9.7 Hz, 9.7 Hz, 9.2 Hz for the gyroscope, accelerometer and linear accelerometer of the Mate 9, i.e. even at low values the reading rate of the “acceleration without g ” remains slightly smaller. Pendulum length l , dimensions a , b and c of the devices, radius of gyration around the y -axis R , eigenfrequency f_0 and damping constant δ are specified in table 1 for both setups. For the calculation of the radius of gyration R the devices were approximated by a homogeneous cuboid.

	iPad	Mate 9
l (mm)	(503 ± 2)	(395 ± 2)
a (mm)	174.1	78.9
b (mm)	250.6	156.9
c (mm)	6.1	7.9
R (mm)	50.3	22.9
(x_S, y_S) (mm)	$(10 \pm 5, 56 \pm 3)$	$(30 \pm 2, 45 \pm 2)$
f_0 (Hz)	(0.697 ± 0.001)	(0.7921 ± 0.0005)
δ (s^{-1})	(0.0023 ± 0.0002)	(0.00135 ± 0.00001)

Table 1: Values for pendulum length l , dimensions a , b , c , gyromagnetic radius $R = \sqrt{(a^2 + c^2)/12}$ for rotation around the y -axis, position of the acceleration sensor (x_S, y_S) , eigenfrequency f_0 and damping constant δ . The dimensions were taken from the manufacturers specifications. The position coordinates of the acceleration sensor were determined experimentally for the iPad [11] and estimated from images of the circuit-board design for the Huawei Mate 9 [12].

3 Results

Data for angular velocity $\vec{\omega}$, acceleration \vec{a} and “acceleration without g ” \vec{b} for the iPad pendulum are shown in Fig. 2 for seven periods. ω_y is the dominating angular velocity vector component, spurious oscillations around the x - and z -axes could not be avoided, but are small. The measured acceleration components are mainly restricted to the x - z -plane, the spurious y components of the acceleration are also small. There are two striking observations: (1) whereas a_x is rather small, b_x is quite sizable. Since b_x is obtained after subtraction of the acceleration of gravity g projected onto the instantaneous direction of the x -axis, this observation indicates that there is some compensation mechanism behind a_x . (2) The variation in b_z is clearly smaller than that in a_z , since the g -component along z was subtracted. Both components oscillate with twice the eigenfrequency [11].

Figure 2: Measurements with an iPad Air: (a)-(c) Angular velocity, (d)-(f) negative acceleration and (g)-(i) negative “acceleration without g ” as a function of time. Symbols represent measured data, solid lines were calculated with Eqs. (3) with $x_S = 0$ (black lines) and $x_S \neq 0$ (green lines). Note the different scales in (d) and (g).

How can these observations be explained? As discussed in many textbooks [3, 13, 14, 15], in the absence of friction, the acceleration of the pendulum $\alpha_y = \ddot{\varphi}_y = \dot{\omega}_y$ is related to the azimuthal g -component by

$$\alpha_y = -gl/(l^2 + R^2) \sin \varphi_y. \quad (1)$$

In the laboratory, the acceleration is given by \vec{g} , in the smartphone accelerated frame of reference the measured acceleration is

$$\vec{a} = \vec{g} - \vec{\omega} \times (\vec{\omega} \times \vec{r}_S) - \vec{\alpha} \times \vec{r}_S \quad (2)$$

with the vector \vec{r}_S pointing from the suspension point to the acceleration sensor, see above. The additional terms on the r.h.s. are due to the centrifugal acceleration and the acceleration generated

Figure 3: Measurements with a Huawei Mate 9: (a)-(c) Angular velocity, (d)-(f) negative acceleration and (g)-(i) negative “acceleration without g ” as a function of time. Symbols represent measured data, solid lines were calculated with Eqs. (3) with $x_S = 0$ (black lines) and $x_S \neq 0$ (green lines). Note the different scales in (d) and (g).

by the angular acceleration $\vec{\alpha}$. The “acceleration without g ” is $\vec{b} = \vec{a} - \vec{g}$ and does only measure the virtual acceleration contributions. With $\vec{\omega} = (0, \omega_y, 0)$ and $\vec{\alpha} = (0, \alpha_y, 0)$, Eq. (2) yields the non-zero acceleration components

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_x &= g \sin \varphi_y + l \dot{\omega}_y + x_S \omega_y^2 = -\frac{R^2}{l} \dot{\omega}_y + x_S \omega_y^2, & b_x &= l \dot{\omega}_y + x_S \omega_y^2 \\
 a_z &= -g \cos \varphi_y - l \omega_y^2 + x_S \dot{\omega}_y, & b_z &= -l \omega_y^2 + x_S \dot{\omega}_y.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The displacement of the acceleration sensor along the y -axis does not affect the acceleration transformation, since it is parallel to the oscillation axis. The measured acceleration components can be modelled with equations (3) using the measured angular velocity component ω_y . The damping is indeed small, see values in table 1, but is implicitly taken into account, since the measured angular velocity is used for modelling. The results are shown in figure 2 as black solid lines for $x_S = 0$ and as green solid lines for the independently measured value of x_S . Taking the displaced sensor position into account leads to an improved modelling of the z -component of the acceleration. b_x mainly measures the virtual acceleration $l \dot{\omega}_y$. This is nearly compensated by the azimuthal component of the acceleration of gravity $g \sin \varphi$ to yield a rather small value of a_x . b_z mainly measures the centrifugal acceleration $l \omega_y^2$, the frequency doubling to $2f_0$ is due to the squaring of the angular velocity [11]. The oscillation in a_z is larger than in b_z , since the vertical component $g \cos \varphi$ of the acceleration of gravity is present and also frequency-doubled, see black lines in Fig. 2(f) and (i). Both b_z and a_z show an additional oscillation with eigenfrequency f_0 that is due to the non-central location of the acceleration sensor within the iPad and is modelled by the term $x_S \dot{\omega}_y$. If this term is taken into account, the green solid lines in figure 2(f) and (i)

are obtained that agree with the measured data rather well.

Equivalent measurements in the same configuration were made with a Huawei Mate 9 smartphone. The experimental results are shown in Fig. 3. These reveal a similar pattern as the iPad results, i.e. ω_y is the dominating component, a_y and b_y are negligible, a_x is considerably smaller than b_x and both a_z and b_z are frequency doubled. However, a_x is not very well compensated. The corresponding modelling with Eqs. (3) is shown in Fig. 3 as black and green lines for $x_S = 0$ and $x_S \neq 0$. Compared to the iPad results, for the Mate 9 the agreement between experimental data and model curves is significantly worse, and least satisfactory for the a_x -data. It is not evident, why this is the case, since the pendulum construction was rather similar. Further, the ratio between gyromagnetic radius and pendulum length that specifies how point-like the pendulum bob is, was $R/l = 0.06$ in case of the Mate 9 and clearly smaller than the iPad value of $R/l = 0.1$. It was verified that the agreement between experimental data and model curves is not influenced by the sensor reading rates. There appears to be a small time lag of the b_x - and b_y -data as inferred from a comparison with the respective acceleration data a_x and a_y as well as the angular velocity ω_y . This time lag can be seen in Fig. 3(g) as a small left-shift of the data curve with respect to the model curve. The time lag is (-0.09 s) at maximum reading rate and (-0.07 s) at the fixed nominal reading rates of 100 Hz and 10 Hz. Curiously, it does not appear in the b_z -component. Since the “acceleration without g” is calculated from the measured acceleration using the instantaneous smartphone orientation, one might speculate that the reduced reading rate of the “acceleration without g” as well as the time lag might be related to resources in computing power allocated to this process. This does not, however, imply a worse agreement between experimental data and modelling, especially since the a_x and a_z -data are not affected by these effects. From Eqs. (1) and (3), a_x should be compensated down to $R^2/(l^2 + R^2) = 0.3\%$ of $g \sin \varphi_y \simeq b_x$, but the comparison between Figs. 3(d) and (g) shows only a reduction down to 16%.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, data of angular velocity, acceleration and “acceleration without g” were measured for two smartphone pendulums using an iPad Air 3 and a Huawei Mate 9. In case of the iPad pendulum the acceleration and “acceleration without g” could be successfully modelled by the transformation into an accelerated frame. Especially the “acceleration without g” data are rather accurate. The data recorded with the Mate 9 pendulum showed similar results. However, the agreement between data and model curves was significantly worse. This finding was discussed, but a reason for these discrepancies could not be identified.

References

- [1] Pendrill A M and Rohlén J 2011 *Phys. Educ.* **46** 676
- [2] Vogt P and Kuhn J 2012 *Phys. Teach.* **50** 439
- [3] 2019 *Physik ganz smart - Die Gesetze der Welt mit dem Smartphone entdecken* ed Kuhn J and Vogt P (Berlin: Springer Spektrum)
- [4] Briggles J 2013 *Phys. Educ.* **48** 285
- [5] Amoroso A and Rinaudo M 2018 *J. Phys.: Conf. Series* **1076** 012013
- [6] Vandermarlière J and Indenbom M 2020 *arXiv:2005.05002*
- [7] Götze B, Heinke H, Riese J, Stampfer C and Kuhlen S 2017 *PhyDid B* <http://www.phydid.de/index.php/phydid-b/article/view/775>
- [8] Kuhn J and Vogt P 2012 *Phys. Teach.* **50** 504

- [9] Castro-Palacio J C, Velázquez-Abad L, Giménez M H and Monsoriu J A 2013 *Am. J. Phys.* **81** 472
- [10] <https://phyphox.org/> retrieved 2020/06/17
- [11] Reinhold S and Ziese M 2021 *Eur. J. Phys.* **42** 025003
- [12] URL <https://de.ifixit.com/Teardown/Huawei+Mate+9+Teardown/98335>
- [13] Alonso M and Finn E J 1992 *Physics* (Harlow: Addison-Wesley)
- [14] Halliday D, Resnick R and Walker J 2008 *Fundamentals of Physics* 8th ed (Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons)
- [15] Tipler P A 1991 *Physics for Scientists and Engineers* 3rd ed (New York: Worth Publishers)